

Discovering skill requirements using AI: DataGEMS, an EU Horizon Project

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Abstract—This paper introduces DataGEMS, an EU Horizon-funded research project focused on data exploration and data discovery. The platform introduces various AI-driven approaches to bridge the gap between data and data-based question-answering systems. DataGEMS is an ongoing project and currently supports four use cases. In this paper, we detail the lifelong learning use case, which compares individuals’ and organizational skill models with reference skill models to identify skill gaps and recommend targeted educational offerings to close them. The use case utilizes natural language questions and a structured set of comparisons to calculate proficiency deltas and match the missing competencies with appropriate educational programs. Additionally, data from diverse sources, including skill taxonomies (ESCO, O*NET), organizational skill models, and educational offerings, support DataGEMS’s data-driven nature. The work presented in this paper highlights skill modeling research and provides a practical AI-driven framework for HR professionals and individuals to navigate continuous up/re skilling requirements driven by automation, AI adoption, and demographic workforce changes.

Index Terms—Lifelong learning, AI, Skill management

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Rapid technological advancement, demographic change, and economic restructuring are fundamentally transforming labor markets and skill requirements worldwide. A significant body of research shows that digital innovation and automation have influenced and altered job task compositions by reducing the demand for routine work in certain occupations, while increasing the demand for analytical problem-solving and interpersonal skills, [1], [2], and [3].

Furthermore, the introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) in recent times has further intensified this transformation of skill requirements. Empirical studies demonstrate that AI complements human labor in some tasks while substituting for it in others, leading to shifting skill requirements rather than uniform job destruction [4]. In particular, AI has created a demand for skills that enable effective human–machine interaction, such as digital literacy, adaptability, and collaborative problem-solving [5]. These trends place sustained pressure on individuals and organizations to continuously acquire and update skills. Societal and demographic factors compound these technological pressures. Workforce aging, increased labor market mobility, and changing career trajectories challenge

traditional education models that focus on learning in early life stages [6].

Research in human resource development emphasizes that lifelong learning, defined as continuous, self-directed, and context-sensitive learning across the lifespan, is critical for maintaining employability and organizational resilience [7]. However, participation in lifelong learning remains uneven, often constrained by limited access to relevant learning opportunities and insufficient alignment between training provision and evolving skill demands [8]. From an organizational perspective, workforce up-skilling is further complicated by the lack of integrated, data-driven approaches for understanding skill evolution. As a result, organizations struggle to translate external technological and economic signals into actionable insights for workforce development. The researcher in [9] proposes a transdisciplinary approach to managing transitions in skill requirements, offering practical strategies for organizations to foster lifelong learning while ensuring fairness and inclusion across diverse demographics.

Together, these societal, technological, and economic dynamics underscore the need for data-centric, AI-supported lifelong learning systems. Such systems must enable continuous skill assessment, anticipate emerging skill needs, and support evidence-based up-skilling strategies at both individual and organizational levels.

B. The DataGEMS Platform

DataGEMS^{1 2} is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. DataGEMS provides tools and mechanisms, powered by AI and data-centric approaches, to address the challenges outlined in the previous section.

DataGEMS is a data discovery platform with Generalized Exploratory, Management, and Search capabilities. It is built on the principles of data FAIRness, openness, and re-use. It aims to seamlessly integrate data sharing, discovery, and analysis into a system that addresses the whole data lifecycle, i.e., sharing, storing, managing, discovering, analyzing, and reusing (data and/or metadata), bridging the gap between the

¹DataGEMS project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 10118841

²<https://datagems.eu/>

data provider and the data consumer. DataGEMS is a next-generation data discovery and management ecosystem that engulfs different types of data (structured, unstructured, real-time and historical) and enables users to (a) enrich data through powerful data profiling mechanisms (b) seamlessly discover and analyze data across and within datasets using user-intuitive discovery and analysis mechanisms, such as using natural language and patterns, and (c) effectively explore and combine data with the help of stepwise guidance mechanisms during dataset discovery and analysis. The effective and efficient functioning of these mechanisms will be enabled by a data and model management layer that decouples low-level data management from higher-level data analytics.

C. Lifelong Learning as a Use Case

Individuals and organizations are constantly challenged to adapt continuously to remain effective and competitive. Given this backdrop, lifelong learning is no longer an individual-centric concept but an organizational requirement, supported by structured models, reliable data, and analytical mechanisms.

DataGEMS will be initially tested and deployed to benefit diverse user communities and user types across core domains: education, meteorology, and language data infrastructures, where the lifelong learning use case is part of the education domain. As one of the use cases for the DataGEMS platform, lifelong learning addresses the aforementioned challenges by analyzing individual and organizational skill models against future skill demands and thereby suggesting appropriate educational offerings to close the skill gap. The underlying idea is to treat skills not as static but as dynamic entities that can be influenced by external events such as technological innovation, legal changes, and shifts in public perception. The overall vision is to enable organizations to better anticipate their skill needs, identify emerging skill gaps, and provide educational solutions to meet these requirements.

The use case builds on the assumption that explicit skill models created using skill management tools represent the skills an individual possesses (given a specific occupation or context). A collection of individual skill models can represent a team or, at a higher level, any organizational unit. Furthermore, these skill models can be reasoned with, i.e., we can perform calculations to get a skill delta, etc. These skill models serve as the foundation for comparison across time, organizational units, and reference frameworks. Some of the key requirements for the comparison include the ability to (i) assess external changes that may affect skill relevance, (ii) assess the impact of such changes on existing skill models, (iii) identify mismatches between current and target skill sets, and (iv) relate identified skill gaps to suitable educational offerings. To achieve the required goals, the use case requires interoperable datasets, such as skill models, skill forecasts, and metadata describing learning opportunities, as well as mechanisms for comparing these models over time. Another key requirement related to skill analysis is the explainability. A stakeholder may not be interested in binary answers to important questions, such as whether certain skills are sufficient or obsolete, but

will also be interested in the rationale behind it, which events, trends, or reference models lead to a particular assessment.

D. Problem Statement and Contributions

The expected outcome of the project and the use case is a comprehensive analytical framework to support human resource planning and workforce development. We envision linking skill model evolution, gap analysis, skill model algebra, and educational recommendations. The use case aims to provide actionable insights for a diverse set of stakeholders, including human resource executives, skill development experts, and individuals. In the process, we contribute to ongoing research on skill modeling, skill gap detection, and AI approaches to lifelong learning while implementing a tool to support continuous up/re-skilling.

II. RELATED WORK

The following section briefly summarizes related work on developing a data-driven learning and knowledge exploration system. Such a system would be at the intersection of multiple domains, including data discovery, question-answering systems, competency-based learning, and adaptive educational technologies. This section reviews the foundational work in these areas.

A. Data Discovery and Knowledge Exploration

The work on data discovery and exploratory data analysis has been central to database research and human-computer interaction; some of the earliest work includes [10], which introduced dynamic queries and visual exploration tools that enabled users to explore large datasets interactively. Furthermore, research has examined reducing the cognitive load of data exploration through intelligent recommendation and automation systems. The authors in [11] developed a mixed-initiative system that combines manual specification with automated chart recommendations for exploratory visual analysis.

Similarly, the AIDE framework proposed by [12], an active-learning-based approach, enables users to explore data interactively and to automatically generate and refine query recommendations. This allows users to iteratively narrow down on their analytical request without requiring an explicit query formulation. The authors in [13] demonstrated that natural language conversational interaction can lower barriers to data analysis for non-technical users. This would enable non-technical users through incremental dialog-driven query refinement. Furthermore, systems like Eviza, presented by the authors [14] at ACM CHI, leverage large language models (LLMs) to enable exploratory question-answering over tabular data. This approach would bridge the gap between structured databases and users asking unstructured questions. They also highlighted the possible use of a conversational paradigm to ease data access. The authors also assume that users possess sufficient domain knowledge to formulate meaningful queries.

B. AI-Based and Data-Rooted Questioning Systems

Question-answering (QA) systems have evolved significantly, from their early template-based approaches to current LLMs, as they have moved from structured and semi-structured data. The authors in [15] developed semantic parsing techniques that map natural-language questions to executable logical forms over knowledge bases, enabling the system to answer complex queries over structured data sources such as Freebase and DBpedia.

The authors in [16] continued the work on semantic parsing for semi-structured tables by introducing the WikiTableQuestions dataset and a logical-form parsing algorithm that can answer complex questions over Wikipedia tables, addressing the dual challenges of broader domain coverage and deep logical computation. More recently, hybrid approaches have combined neural generation with non-parametric retrieval. [17] Introduced Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) at NeurIPS, a framework that uses pre-trained parametric memory with a dense non-parametric retrieval index; this process significantly improves the performance on information-intensive question answering tasks. The interface for QA systems introduces additional complexity by requiring context tracking, referencing resolution, and a way to clarify the query. [18] developed and proposed a conversational QA system that maintains dialogue memory across turns, which enables users to ask follow-up questions without rephrasing the context.

Similarly, there have been hybrid approaches that combine retrieval from unstructured text with querying structured knowledge bases. [19], who proposed GRAFT-Net, a graph neural network model that fuses knowledge base entities and text passages into a unified question-specific subgraph to answer open-domain questions. Although there have been advancements in existing systems, QA systems face various challenges. Particularly in reasoning and representation of structured domain knowledge, as highlighted by [20] in their exhaustive review of knowledge graphs (KDs), their history, and their role in organizing world knowledge for AI systems

C. Skill-Based Learning and Competency-Driven Platforms

The landscape of educational technology has witnessed a monumental shift from content-centric to skill-centric learning models. The authors in [21] laid the foundational work for evidence-centered design for learning, proposing a framework that links observable student behaviors to underlying competencies through probabilistic reasoning. Further building on this, competency-based education (CBE) models prioritize the mastery of specific skills, enabling personalized learning pathways, as surveyed by [22] in the Journal of Competency-Based Education. Additionally, [23] proposed an ontology-based competency framework in the Journal of Interactive Learning Research that formalized the relationships among tasks, skills, and learning resources, facilitating advanced content recommendation and gap analysis. There has been significant research on competency frameworks and skill taxonomies across domains. The European e-Competence Framework (e-CF), developed by the CEN Workshop on ICT Skills [24],

and O*NET [25] in the United States, provides standardized taxonomies of professional skills.

Jovanovic et al. [26] used learning analytics to model a learner's competencies dynamically. The system used trace data from the interactions with the digital platform to infer skill levels and predict performance. Furthermore, Khosravi et al. [27] published research on an adaptive learning system with intelligent feedback mechanisms that enable real-time personalization based on learners' engagement patterns and performance.

Positioning relative to prior work. The skill gap algebra introduced here builds on earlier studies but remains distinct from prior competency-related models. For example, Paquette's ontology-based framework [23] standardises professional and educational competencies digitally. In this framework, skills are modeled as ontological entities, supporting reasoning over them. This ontology-driven architecture enables personalised lifelong learning. Our approach differs by introducing gap operators as a first step towards an algebra defined for skill models. Our main contributions: (i) taxonomy-agnostic projection operators for extracting and normalising skills, (ii) proficiency-aware skill gap operators (\square and \square^-) that distinguish missing from under-proficient skills, and (iii) combining identified gaps with educational offerings via a natural-language querying pipeline. DataGEMS makes gap calculation algebraically explicit and auditable, thereby supporting explainability.

D. Data Sources for Lifelong Learning Systems

Lifelong learning systems require diverse data sources to model learners' competencies (skill levels), recommend learning pathways, and align educational offerings with labor market demands. Skill models and competency frameworks, such as those derived from ESCO (European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations) [28] and [29], analyzed skill taxonomies from job boards such as LinkedIn and Glassdoor to provide structured representations of skill requirements. These frameworks, among others, help design and enable systems to map a learner's profile to the requirements for a job and identify gaps. Janssen et al. [30] explored the use of organizational learning data, including performance reviews, project assignments, and peer feedback, to identify skills and competencies that a formal assessment may not capture.

The data generated and captured through learners' interactions with learning management systems, MOOCs, and workplace platforms offer a great opportunity for personalized recommendations. Pardos and Heffernan [31] demonstrated that fine-grained clickstream data can be used to reveal learning patterns through User Modeling and User-Adapted Interaction. Frey and Osborne [32] published their seminal work on technological forecasting and social change regarding the future of employment, highlighting the skills at risk of automation. Further, studies by Deming [33] in the Quarterly Journal of Economics and the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report [34] track emerging competencies in areas such as AI literacy, data science, and human-centered design.

Additionally, integrating such skill forecast data into learning systems will enable proactive skill development, as de Fareri et al. [35] demonstrated in their study on AI-driven career guidance. The work we carry out as part of DataGEMS unifies these conversational frameworks by leveraging skill models. Working with these diverse research streams and data sources, DataGEMS aims to address critical gaps at the intersection, enable data exploration, and build a QA system bounded by competencies to users’ learning requirements.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Design Principles and Assumptions

The DataGEMS platform comprises multiple components. For each component, a boundary has been defined with clear inputs and outputs. Given that the platform is distributed, spanning multiple contributors and partners, the platform components are designed for loose coupling. The platform is designed using a microservice architecture paradigm.

The Model Context Protocol (MCP) [36] is a universal protocol that standardizes the definition, discovery, and structured interaction of AI models, particularly LLMs, with external tools and execution environments. In the proposed architecture for DataGEMS, the MCP servers provide a registry of tools with their standard description and specify each tool’s purpose, expected inputs, and outputs. On the client side, the MCP is responsible for correctly reading the registry and invoking the appropriate tools based on the task at hand. Within the architecture of the DataGEMS platform, MCP will be used to expose a set of tools that provide access and data preprocessing capabilities. These tools can be invoked by the components based on user queries. Another core idea of the architecture is the MoMA (Model of Metadata and data) logical model. It is a graph-based data model that represents datasets, metadata, machine-learned models, and all the operations that can be performed on the data. Moma enables the platform to handle heterogeneous datasets (e.g., text, images, sensor data, and structured SQL, NoSQL, and graph data).

B. Conceptual Architecture of the DataGEMS Platform

The primary software deliverable of the DataGEMS project is the DataGEMS platform, which will also be part of the EOSC³ infrastructure. DataGEMS will support users in publishing, discovering, and using datasets across diverse domains. As mentioned earlier, the platform has a microservices architecture, where all components expose REST API endpoints to ensure scalability, modularity, and ease of integration.

As illustrated in the logical architecture overview in Figure 1, the platform’s coarse-grained structure reflects its core responsibilities and interaction model. There are two primary user roles for the platform: The consumer, who searches for datasets to answer dataset exploration and discovery questions, or to support data-driven tasks. The second group of users is the providers, who contribute datasets to the platform. Within the DataGEMS project, the key providers also originate from

the use cases. The platform currently supports the following use cases: Mathematics, Weather, Language, and Lifelong Learning (DHBW). Furthermore, there are two main entry points for the DataGEMS platform: the DataGEMS UI and the DataGEMS API. The DataGEMS UI provides a single-page application that offers a cohesive, interactive experience. This interface enables key platform functionalities, including dataset ingestion, search, exploration, and metadata enrichment. All UI interactions are mediated by the DataGEMS Gateway, which serves as the platform’s central point of interaction.

In addition, the DataGEMS platform offers developers and third-party integrators programmatic access via its DataGEMS API, which the DataGEMS Gateway exposes. The DataGEMS Gateway authenticates users via the DataGEMS AAI, enforces access control policies, and orchestrates the user’s journey through the platform’s services. Behind the gateway, the platform is composed of a set of semantically grouped microservices, organized into four main categories:

- Dataset Profiling: analyzing and extracting metadata from contributed datasets and linking them with each other.
- Dataset Discovery: discover datasets, ask questions on data, and produce datasets.
- User Assistance: assist the user via recommendations of datasets and queries, provenance of data discovery actions.
- Data Storing & Management: handling storage, metadata persistence, and data governance.

Finally, we have the data set layer, which stores all data and metadata. In Figure 1, all microservices can access the datasets directly if required, as per their requirements.

C. Separation of data ingestion, processing, and User interface

At the core of the DataGEMS platform is the data and management layer. This layer is fundamental to realizing the platform’s vision of seamless data discovery and analysis. It achieves this by decoupling low-level data management, responsible for storing and brokering data and machine learning models, from higher-level analytics and discovery functionalities. By decoupling the LLM’s prompts and logic from the tool’s implementation details, MCP simplifies integration and reduces the need for custom, tightly coupled solutions. Through this architectural separation, the platform can interconnect the components that are responsible for:

- Enriching dataset metadata through data profiling and quality monitoring.
- Cross-dataset and in-dataset discovery operators powered by ad-hoc indexes as well as stored machine learning models.
- Personalized support of data exploration workflows via query and dataset recommender systems.
- Polyglot querying capabilities that unify access to heterogeneous data stored in files, databases, and real-time streams.

³<https://eosc.eu/>

- Storing, cataloging, and serving machine learning models and their connections to datasets.

The Data Storage, Management, and Access components form the technical backbone on which various components are implemented to provide these functionalities.

The DataGEMS architecture is designed to be general in the functionality it offers, and the components provide use-case-agnostic functionality. The combination of domain-specific datasets, any required pre-processing steps, and use-case-specific interfacing components enables the general DataGEMS platform to deliver tailored functionality that addresses use-case-specific requirements. Outside of these domains, the DataGEMS operators are designed to be extensible and composable, enabling the onboarding, discovery, and exploration of data from different use cases.

The User interface component is still under review; however, the current version is illustrated in Figure 2 where the user can explore the stored datasets and ask questions directly to the DataGEMS platform.

Fig. 2. Lifelong learning User interface (image retrieved from internal DataGEMS project documentation).

Fig. 1. DataGEMS architecture overview (image retrieved from internal DataGEMS project documentation).

IV. CASE STUDY (LIFELONG LEARNING)

A. Workforce Up-skilling Challenges and Skill Models

The unprecedented shift in technology, particularly the adoption of automation and AI, is continuously reshaping workforce requirements, meaning that a significant portion of the current workforce needs re-skilling to remain employable [37]. Furthermore, there are organizational hurdles, such as inadequate funding and resistance to change, which often undermine upskilling and reskilling initiatives [38]. Studies also show that current training programs may lack relevance to current labor market requirements, which, in turn, causes a persistent skills shortage [39]. Furthermore, misalignment between educational curricula and industry demands continues to challenge comprehensive up/re-skilling strategies [40]. To address these issues, the lifelong learning use case as part of the DataGEMS project, has devised the following strategy, where an individual can submit their skill model and get an updated list of education offerings that can fulfill the missing

skill gaps or organizational head trying to up/re-skill their work force could upload an organizational skill model and receive a detailed report to address the organizational skill gap. The following sections go into detail about the individual scenario as an example.

The European Skills, Competences, Qualifications and Occupations organization (ESCO) [41] defines:

- Skill: Is the ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems.
- Competence: Is the proven ability to use knowledge, skills, and personal, social, and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and in professional and personal development.
- Occupation: is a grouping of jobs involving similar tasks and which require a similar skills set.

Furthermore, a skill is usually not a single entity or ability. It is a multifaceted construct with several components. The authors in [42] take a very comprehensive view of the definition of a skill. It has a proficiency level, which is achieved through practice and repetition. A skill is not only a technical ability; it also involves cognitive and behavioral components. This comprehensive definition motivates us to explore further and understand skill gaps and how to mitigate them. Further definitions relevant for the case study:

- Skills taxonomy: is a structured list of skills.
- Skill model/profile: is a subset of skills (from a skill taxonomy) that an individual possesses, defined in a structured format.
- Reference skill model: is an up-to-date list of skills for any given job, derived from a specific taxonomy,

The Figure 3 depicts a custom skill model prepared using the 'myskillsplus' tool [43]. and Figure 4 refers to the skill requirements (reference model) for a data scientist according

to the O*NET taxonomy [25]. Both images contain only a part of the entire skill model.

Tools, Technologies, Applications

Edge AI and On-Device AI SDKs	Basic/Learning	
Computer Vision Tools	Expert/In-depth	
Computer Vision and Image Processing Libraries	Expert/In-depth	
Time-Series Analysis and Forecasting Tools	Proficient/High Level Knowledge	
Quantum AI and Quantum Machine Learning Tools	Basic/Learning	
Graph Neural Networks (GNN) Frameworks	Familiar/Low Level Knowledge	
Reinforcement Learning Tools	Familiar/Low Level Knowledge	
AI/ML Frameworks and Libraries	Proficient/High Level Knowledge	
Prompt Engineering Tools and IDEs	Familiar/Low Level Knowledge	

Fig. 3. Snapshot of a skill model for a data scientist [43]. On the left-hand side are the skills, and a proficiency level is attached to each.

Technology Skills		
15-2051.00 - Data Scientists		
Section	Category	Example
Technology	Analytical or scientific software	IBM SPSS Statistics
Technology	Analytical or scientific software	SAS
Technology	Analytical or scientific software	TensorFlow
Technology	Analytical or scientific software	The MathWorks MATLAB
Technology	Application server software	Docker
Technology	Application server software	GitHub
Technology	Application server software	Kubernetes
Technology	Business intelligence and data analysis software	Alteryx software
Technology	Business intelligence and data analysis software	Apache Spark
Technology	Business intelligence and data analysis software	Microsoft Power BI
Technology	Business intelligence and data analysis software	Tableau
Technology	Cloud-based management software	Amazon Web Services AWS SageMaker
Technology	Cloud-based management software	Google Cloud software
Technology	Content workflow software	Atlassian JIRA

Fig. 4. Snapshot of a reference skill model for a data scientist according to O*NET [25].

B. Use Case Setup and Data

The use case is intended primarily for hiring managers and human resource professionals. Hence, the underlying assumption is that platform users will have access to skill management tools (e.g., Muschskills⁴) for creating skill models. The Figure 5 depicts the process of creating a skill model for an individual. Furthermore, a collection of such individual skill models(for each employee) would create an organizational skill model.

Another important pillar for the use case is educational offerings, which help fill skill gaps. Apart from skill models (individual, organizational, and reference), educational offerings are the other essential data of the use case. An educational

⁴<https://www.muchskills.com/>

Fig. 5. Skill model creation process.

offering may consist of information about an institution’s courses.

C. User Interaction and Natural Language-Based Querying

This section details the user’s interaction with the DataGEMS platform. As mentioned previously, the assumption is that the user possesses their skill model. So, the required input data are the skill model, Target Occupation (the occupations the user wants to fulfill skills for), and a set of reference models. The user then asks a question in natural language; Figure 6 explains the process. Since natural language questions can be ambiguous, a disambiguation component is required to identify the user’s intent. DataGEMS provides a query disambiguation mechanism that is triggered when the question is identified as ambiguous or too challenging to process as-is. There are other requirements, such as support for questioning in multiple languages, understanding the context of the questions, and understanding slang, etc. The query disambiguation also handles these. Once the question has been disambiguated and processed internally. The response is generated, containing the skill gaps for each available reference model. Furthermore, the user can continue to ask questions about ways to address the missing skills, and the expected output is a list of educational offerings that can be filtered, as shown in Figure 7. Lastly, the user can select the most convenient educational offering and, based on that selection, ask further questions about which skills each offering covers, as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 6. The user provides their skill model, target occupation(s), select reference model and provide a natural language question

D. Analytical Logic

The core analytical mechanism behind the use case is a structured comparison between a reference skill model and

Fig. 7. The user can continue and ask how to fill the missing gaps.

Fig. 8. The user can still refine the request by asking about each educational offering and the skills provided by it.

an individual skill profile. Since the user-provided model may originate from heterogeneous taxonomies, skill identifiers are first aligned to a common reference framework, and the further process is defined in the following sections.

E. Skill Set Definitions

Given a skill identifier 's' and a skill proficiency level 'l(s)'. We define *skill proficiency sets* (skill models/profiles) as P as sets of pairs (s, l(s)) :

$$P = \{(s_i, \ell(s_i))\}$$

In the following we will differentiate skill proficiency sets of individuals I and reference skill proficiency sets R. We assume that a skill identifier s is only part of a single pair (s, l(s)) in a skill proficiency set. The proficiency level associated with a skill identifier s in a skill proficiency set P is denoted by $\ell_p(s)$.

$$R = \{(s_i, \ell_R(s_i)) \mid s_i \text{ required for a target role}\}$$

$$I = \{(s_i, \ell_I(s_i)) \mid s_i \text{ possessed by an individual}\}$$

Furthermore, we define S as a set of skill identifiers and a skill projection operator π , which extracts the set of skill identifiers from a skill proficiency set

$$\pi(P) = \{\forall s_i \mid \exists (s_i, \ell(s_i)) \in P\}$$

Applying π to R and I yields the skill identifier sets $S_R = \pi(R)$, $S_I = \pi(I)$

F. Skill gap calculation

We define *basic skill gap intersection* operator \sqcap that compares skill sets at the identifier level:

$$A \sqcap B = \{(s_i, \ell(s_i)) \mid s_i \in B \wedge s_i \notin A\}$$

We further define the *proficiency gap intersection* intersection that compares skill sets at both the identifier and proficiency level:

$$A \sqcap^- B = \{(s_i, \ell_B(s_i)) \mid s_i \in (S_A \cap S_B) \wedge \ell_A(s_i) < \ell_B(s_i)\}$$

which captures skills present in both sets, but where proficiency is below the required level.

1. Set-Level Skill Gap (Missing Skills)

Skills that are fully absent from the individual profile — neither the skill nor any proficiency level is present:

$$G_{\text{set}}(I, R) = I \sqcap R$$

That is, G_{set} contains all required skill-proficiency pairs $(s_i, \ell_R(s_i))$ for which no entry exists in I whatsoever.

2. Level-Based Skill Gap (Proficiency Below Requirement)

Skills present in the individual profile but whose proficiency does not meet the requirement:

$$G_{\text{level}}(I, R) = I \sqcap^- R$$

The skill exists in the individual's profile, but $\ell_R(s_i) > \ell_I(s_i)$ indicates the proficiency is below what the role demands.

3. Outdated Skills

Skills present in the individual's profile but not required by the target role neither the skill nor its associated proficiency level appears in R:

$$G_{\text{out}}(I, R) = R \sqcap I$$

A skill is considered outdated if at least one of the following conditions holds:

- 1) The skill is not required in the current reference model due to technological innovation and legal changes.
- 2) The skill has low or zero demand frequency across the organization's reference models.
- 3) The skill is marked as deprecated in the reference taxonomy (e.g., replaced by a successor skill).

Calculate the skill gap: Once skills and proficiency levels are aligned, the system computes the skill gap as the union of G_{set} and G_{level} . Furthermore, these calculations are limited to individuals and can be generalized to organizations.

G. Worked Example

To illustrate the formal definitions, consider a simplified scenario with three skills s_1 (Python p), s_2 (Machine Learning), and s_3 (Communication), where proficiency levels range from 1 (beginner) to 5 (expert). Let the reference skill set for a data scientist role R and an individual's profile I be:

$$R = \{(s_1, 4), (s_2, 3), (s_3, 2)\}$$

$$I = \{(s_1, 2), (s_3, 2)\}$$

Applying π yields $\mathcal{S}_R = \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$ and $\mathcal{S}_I = \{s_1, s_3\}$.

Set-level gap (missing skills): $s_2 \notin \mathcal{S}_I$, so $G_{\text{set}}(I, R) = \{(s_2, 3)\}$.

Level-based gap (insufficient proficiency): $s_1 \in \mathcal{S}_R \cap \mathcal{S}_I$ and $\ell_R(s_1) = 4 > \ell_I(s_1) = 2$, so $G_{\text{level}}(I, R) = \{(s_1, 4)\}$.

Outdated skills: all skills in \mathcal{S}_I are present in \mathcal{S}_R , so $G_{\text{out}}(I, R) = \emptyset$.

The overall skill gap is $G_{\text{set}} \cup G_{\text{level}} = \{(s_2, 3), (s_1, 4)\}$, which the system then uses to retrieve matching educational offerings.

H. Workflow Overview

The workflow begins by retrieving two skill models. The stored reference skill model, which is associated with an occupation or a role, as well as the user's individual skill model. And secondly, the educational offerings, further process is as follows:

- *Extraction of skill and proficiency levels*: from both the reference and individual skill models, the system extracts a list of skills and their associated proficiency levels.
- *Calculate the skill gap*: Once skills and proficiency levels are aligned, the system calculates the skill gap by comparing required levels against current levels for each skill
- *Match missing skills with training offerings*: For each identified gap, the system searches educational repositories and metadata sources to identify training offerings that address the missing or insufficient skills.
- *Generate a suitable list of education offerings*: Finally, the system compiles an appropriate list of educational offerings that can fill the gap. The list will support filters such as formats, duration, language, and cost.

V. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The DataGEMS platform and the lifelong learning use case are currently under development. Hence, certain limitations should be noted. The proposed framework and architecture will be tested in real-world scenarios. As a result, assertions around usability and effectiveness require further validation and empirical evaluation.

Additionally, the skill gap operators assume skill identifiers come from heterogeneous taxonomies such as ESCO, O*NET, and custom organizational models. These identifiers can be aligned into a common reference space. In practice, the alignment process can introduce errors and affect the accuracy of gap calculations.

Currently, proficiency levels are directly comparable as integers across taxonomies. However, proficiency levels could be defined differently. In that case, a rigorous cross-taxonomy normalization or mapping is necessary. Using alternative definitions may reduce the accuracy and reliability of the gap calculation.

Planned evaluation steps include deploying the platform within the EOSC infrastructure. Subsequently, the platform will be evaluated with DHBW's partner organizations. These activities will include multiple pilot studies. Specifically, key themes are: (i) a user study with HR professionals and individuals to assess usability for individual and organizational skill profiles; (ii) evaluation of the accuracy of retrieved information in simple and complex scenarios; and (iii) end-to-end assessment of recommended educational offerings. Together, these evaluations will validate the proposed approaches and provide empirical support for further research and platform development.

VI. CONCLUSION

There has been an accelerated pace of adoption of digital technologies such as AI and automation. This high-paced adoption requires both organizations and individuals to continuously reassess their skill portfolios. To address these challenges, the paper introduces the DataGEMS platform and the Lifelong learning use case. The DataGEMS platform's data-centric approach and AI-assisted nature are used to detect dynamic skill gaps and provide targeted educational recommendations. The proposed approach explores combining structured skill models, taxonomies, and educational offerings with unstructured natural-language questions for data-driven workforce planning. The structured set comparison and the calculation of proficiency delta/skill gap allow individuals and organizations to identify partial and full skill gaps. The skill gap calculations help prioritize human resource development needs and align with upskilling programs.

As the platform is powered by AI-supported natural language querying capabilities, the barrier to interacting with the system is lower, enabling intuitive interaction and the ability to ask complex questions. From an organizational perspective, the platform supports proactive workforce planning, strategic re-skilling and up-skilling, and improved allocation of training resources. For educational institutions and training providers, it enables listing educational offerings and promoting skill-aligned course descriptions, helping better align courses with labor market demands. Formally, the integration of data discovery, skill modeling, and AI-enabled search advances research at the intersection of data management, question-answering systems, and lifelong learning technologies.

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